

Determination of Temperature Coefficient of Palladium Catalyst on Alumina Support

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STUDIES on oxidation of methane and other hydrocarbon on palladium surface by micro calorimetric bead technique have been widely reported^{1,2}. Almost in every method, employed for study of kinetics using catalytic bead, temperature of catalytic surface has been directly measured or estimated using standard equation of platinum resistance thermometer^{2,3}. No attempt has been made to evaluate the temperature coefficient of calorimetric bead of palladium catalyst on alumina support. In the present study the same has been determined using standard equation, the value so determined was found to be varying with that for platinum, employed as a coil.

Experimental

The preparation of microcalorimetric bead (2-3 mm in length) used for the catalytic studies has been described by authors⁵ and other workers⁴. Other experimental arrangement for determination of temperature coefficient of bead has been shown in Fig. 1. For lower temperature ranges the bead

Fig. 1

terminals were soldered to 30 SWG copper wire and for higher temperature range contact arrangements were made. The copper terminals for bead and compensator were embedded in a asbestos plug to ensure rigidity, kept in a glass furnace having volume 500 ml and with a provision for heating up to 500°. The temperature of the furnace was controlled by Sunvic temperature controller, the temperature variation were recorded by precision thermometer. Resistances were measured with a Resistance Bridge.

Results and Discussion

Measurement of resistances with temperature variation for (a) platinum coil, (b) an alumina bead, (c) palladium coated bead of alumina were made at every 10° and 20° rise and at each temperature; average of ten readings were taken.

Using standard equation the values of temperature coefficient for three different materials were calculated between 40° and 50° and found to be .0028, .00169, .0024 respectively for platinum coil, alumina bead and palladium coated alumina bead. Values of temperature coefficient when calculated for wider range of temperature did not have very good agreement with measurement at lower temperature. This could be due to fluctuations in temperature at higher temperature.

With values so determined for temperature coefficients one can easily evaluate the surface temperature of such microcatalytic bead. Further attempt is being made to co-relate experimentally the temperature calculated from coefficient values and with those determined by I.R. and thermo-couple technique.

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Physico-chemical Properties of Magnesium Soaps of Lower Fatty Acids in Alcohols

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MAGNESIUM soaps find frequent use in greases¹⁻⁴, paints and varnishes⁵, catalytic actions⁶⁻⁸, etc. Their applications make it so important that it attracted the attention to study the properties in various solvents. Recently the behaviour of magnesium soaps of lower fatty acids in water has been-

TABLE—1
 Temperature $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Soap	CMC in moles litre ⁻¹	B	$\Delta_{M=1}$	K	Δ_∞	X	$Y \times 10^4$
<i>2-methyl-1-propanol</i>							
Valerate	0.010	0.52	0.44	3.95×10^{-7}	89.99	0.021	12.74
Caproate	0.010	0.59	0.28	2.11×10^{-7}	51.42	0.021	8.18
Caprylate	0.008	0.60	0.25	3.84×10^{-7}	18.82	0.021	5.74
<i>3-methyl-1-butanol</i>							
Valerate	0.010	0.59	0.24	0.93×10^{-7}	71.66	0.014	9.46
Caproate	0.010	0.64	0.17	0.92×10^{-7}	69.08	0.013	3.50
Caprylate	0.005	0.70	0.11	1.04×10^{-7}	62.00	0.014	3.02
<i>Benzyl alcohol</i>							
Valerate	0.010	—	—	12.60×10^{-8}	0.47	0.02	24.77
Caproate	0.010	—	—	6.94×10^{-8}	0.24	0.019	20.51
Caprylate	0.004	—	—	1.82×10^{-8}	0.17	0.019	19.00

reported^{9,10}. Besides a few references^{11,12} on the properties of magnesium soaps of higher fatty acids in organic solvents, only a little work¹³ on the lower fatty acid soaps is available. The present communication deals with the physical properties of these soaps in alcohols with a view (i) to determine micellar aggregation, dissociation constant, K and molar conductance at infinite dilution, Λ_∞ and (ii) to find the size and nature of the micelles.

Experimental

The chemicals have been purified and the soaps prepared by the method described earlier¹³. All the measurements have been made in a thermostat at a constant temperature ($35 \pm 0.05^\circ$). A conductivity bridge (Philips, PR 9500, India) and a dipping type conductivity cell with platinized electrodes have been used for measuring the conductivity of the soap solutions. The surface tensions of these solutions have been determined by stalagmometer. Several measurements are made to ascertain the reproducibility of results.

Results and Discussion

Conductivity

Specific conductivity, k increases with increasing concentration of the soap solution and the k - C plots (Fig. 1) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite concentration corresponding to CMC (Table 1). The values of CMC of valerate and caproate remain the same but these values of caprylate vary in different alcohols. Similar results (0.01M for valerate and caproate and .005M for caprylate) have been reported⁹ in water. The reason for similarity in the observed CMC for valerate and caproate in various solvents may be due to small difference in the chain length.

Fig. 1. Plots of Specific Conductivity, k ($\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) and Surface Tension, γ (dynes cm^{-1}) vs Concentration, C of Magnesium Soaps (moles litre⁻¹) in 2-Methyl-1-Propanol at 35° .

● Valerate × Caproate ○ Caprylate

Molar conductivity, Λ , calculated from measured specific conductance of solutions decreases with increasing concentration of soap. The plots of Λ vs $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$ are concave curves which is due to the weak electrolyte behaviour of these soaps in alcohols.

A plot of $\log \Lambda$ vs $\log C$ yields straight lines in 2-methyl-1-propanol and 3-methyl-1-butanol which indicates that Λ and C can be related in these alcohols as :

$$\log \Lambda = A + B \log C \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where A and B are constants.

The values of $\log \Lambda$ for zero values of $\log C$ (i.e., for $C=1$) have been found by extrapolation

and the values of Δ_{M-1} ($=A$) are given in Table 1. It is important to note that it is not possible to prepare soap solutions of such a high concentration (1M). These values cannot be determined experimentally. Table 1 shows that the values of $\Delta_M=1$ in 2-methyl-1-propanol are higher than 3-methyl-1-butanol and decrease with increasing chain length of the soap. The mobility of soap cation is reduced due to large viscosity and interionic forces. Constant B increases with increasing chain length of soaps in both the alcohols.

Since the soap behaves as weak electrolyte in dilute solutions and therefore the following expression^{1,2} can be derived :

$$C^2\Delta^2 = \frac{K\Lambda_\infty^2}{4\Lambda} - \frac{\Lambda_\infty^2 K}{4} \quad \dots \dots \quad (ii)$$

The plots of $C^2\Delta^2$ vs $1/\Lambda$ are linear below CMC and equation fails above this concentration. The values of dissociation constant, K and molar conductivity at infinite dilution, Λ_∞ have been obtained from the intercepts and slopes of plots and are given in Table 1. A perusal of this table shows that the values of K of valerate and caproate are almost the same but are lower than caprylate in aliphatic alcohols. A comparison of the values of K shows that these are in the following order :

Benzyl alcohol > 2-methyl-1-propanol > 3-methyl-1-butanol.

Molar conductivity at infinite dilution decreases with increasing chain length of the soap. This may be due to the sluggish motion of the large soap cations, dielectric and other effects. It is observed that the values of Λ_∞ in aliphatic alcohols are much higher than that of benzyl alcohol.

Surface Tension :

Surface tension, γ of the soap solutions decreases with increasing concentration which may be due to the decreasing effects in the surface energy of the solvents. This effect shows the surface active behaviour of the soap. The γ -C plots (Fig. 1) show a sharp change in surface deficiency of the soap at CMC in different solvents.

The following^{1,4} equation has been used for the interpretation of surface tension data

$$\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} = 1 - \frac{KTn_s}{\gamma_0} - \ln\left(1 + \frac{n_s}{K}\right) \quad \dots \dots \quad (iii)$$

where n_s is the number of exposed solvent sites per cm^2 of its surface, n_2 is the concentration of the substrate molecule cm^{-3} in bulk, K is a constant for the solvent and the other terms have their usual significances.

Substituting

$$\frac{KTn_s}{\gamma_0} = X \text{ and } \frac{n_2}{K} = \frac{C}{Y}. \text{ One obtains :}$$

$$\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} = 1 - X \ln(1 + C/Y) \quad \dots \dots \quad (iv)$$

Applying the condition $\frac{C}{Y} \gg 1$, the following approximate expression which Langmuir^{1,5} showed to apply at high solute concentration and in condition of surface saturation was obtained :

$$\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} = 1 - X \ln \frac{C}{Y} \quad \dots \dots \quad (V)$$

where γ and γ_0 are the surface tensions of solutions of concentration C and of pure solvents, respectively. The plots of γ vs $\log C$ are linear which shows that the results are in agreement with the above equation(V). The values of X and Y have been calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the linear γ - $\log C$ plots and the results are given in Table 1.

A perusal of Table 1 shows that X remains constant with increasing soap chain which shows that the number of exposed solvent sites per cm^2 of its surface are almost the same in all the soaps. However, these values in 2-methyl-1-propanol and benzyl alcohol are higher than 3-methyl-1-butanol. This variation occurs due to difference in the values of γ_0 . The parameter Y decreases with increasing chain length of soap due to increasing substrate molecules per ml in the bulk and are in the following order in different solvents

Benzyl alcohol > 2-methyl-1-propanol > 3-methyl-1-butanol.

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Paper Chromatographic Separations of Some Metallic Ions using Penicillins

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SEPARATIONS of certain metal ions, important for the composition of certain special alloys, have been affected using solutions of penicillins as the mobile phase. This underlines, in continuation of our previous communications¹⁻⁴ (related with the study of the potentiality of penicillins as analytical reagent) utility of the same as chromatographic reagent.

A.R. grade metallic salts were used to prepare 0.1M solutions of the metallic ions. The paper used in the study was Whatman No. 1 chromatographic paper. Fe(III), Cu(II), Ag(I) and Cr(III) were detected with the help of the characteristic colours they give with penicillins [Fe(III), reddish brown; Cr(III), greyish green; Ag(I), pale and Cu(II), olive green], while the other metallic ions were detected using usual spotting reagents⁵.

The metallic ions tried in this study were Be (II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Pb(II), Cr(III), Al(III), Fe(III), Ag(I), Mo(VI) and W(VI).

Impregnated papers were prepared by soaking the paper in 2% (W/V) aqueous solutions of Na or K salts of penicillin - G (PG) or penicillin - V (PV) and drying them at room temperature in a dust free chamber.

The mobile phase used with the plain paper include 0.02 M and 0.01 M aqueous solutions of Na/

K-PG and -PV and 1 : 1 mixtures of 0.01 M aqueous penicillins (PG or PV) with ethanol and acetone; while pure organic solvents including a range of polar solvents with donor properties - ethanol, acetone, chloroform and ethyl acetate - were used with the impregnated papers.

Chromatograms using both descending and disc techniques were prepared and Rf-values noted.

Results and Discussion

A comparison of Rf-values obtained in this study indicate that effective separations of certain closely resembling metallic ions (some of them very important for the composition of certain technologically important alloys) can be affected using aqueous solutions of penicillins-G or -V on filter paper strips by descending method. While, the results obtained with radial development technique⁶, using plain and impregnated paper discs showed, although the mobilities of metal ions were found faster on plain papers with the use of aqueous solutions of the penicillins, better separations with least diffusion were obtained using 1 : 1 mixtures (V/V) of the aqueous solutions of PG or PV with ethanol or acetone. On impregnated papers while, chloroform and ethyl acetate failed to give mobility to the metal ions, ethanol and acetone could give sufficient mobilities of the ions and effect separations.

The faster mobilities of metal ions affecting better separations with the use of solutions of penicillins (pure or in 1 : 1 mixtures with ethanol or acetone) can be understood in the light of following mechanism. On plain papers the metal ions in the form of aquo-cations are absorbed with the formation of ion associated metal cellulose bond⁷. On irrigating the paper with solutions of penicillins, the penicillin molecules form complexes with the metal cations displacing the coordinated aquo-molecules partially or wholly. Thus the metal ions get desorbed and are washed away with the solvent. A similar mechanism works on impregnated paper, where the presence of penicillin molecules on the paper shields the metal ion from forming ion associated bond with cellulose. During spotting of the metal ion, the penicillin molecules present on paper form metal-ligand complex with the metal ion. The metal ion thus remains in desorbed state, which is then washed away with the solvent due to its solvating effect. The poor or no mobilities of metallic ions with chloroform and ethyl acetate was found related with the insolubilities of the metal penicillin adducts in these solvents; ethanol and acetone due to their sufficient solvating effect to these metal adducts could give faster mobilities and more effective separations. The separational possibilities of some of the closely resembling ions are summarised in the Table 1.

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